

Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) – Humak Action plan 2024-2028

Organisation	Humak University of Applied Sciences
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1. Introduction

The Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment sets a common path towards changes in assessment practices for research, researchers and research performing organisations. The main aim is to maximise the quality and impact of research. The work towards the Agreement was started in 2022 through which signatory organisations can become members of the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA). The Agreement paves the way for organisations to work together towards the implementation of needed changes in Responsible Research Assessment (RRA).

Humak signed the Agreement in June 2023. Therefore, Humak is committed to the following CoARA commitments:

- Key commitments
 - Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research
 - Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
 - Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index
 - Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment
- Supporting commitments
 - Commit resources to reforming research assessment as is needed to achieve the organisational changes committed to
 - Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes
 - Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use
 - Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition
 - Communicate progress made on adherence to the Principles and implementation of the Commitments
 - Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research

In the context of CoARA, all the signatories commit to share their organisation's plans for implementation of the core commitments in form of an Action Plan. This Action Plan must include defined milestones

regarding the RRA development work and be published within one year of signing the agreement. Signatories commit to regularly demonstrate the progress of development of evaluation criteria, processes and tools that fulfil the core commitments. Within five years of signing the agreement at least one cycle of review and development of the assessment criteria, tools and processes must be gone through.

2. Current situation

Humak is committed to the principles of open science and research and to promoting them in its activities. Humak's culture is built on open sharing of knowledge and expertise and the development of new knowledge in networks. [Humak's principles of openness](#) have been approved by the Humak Executive Team on 17 August 2017. Humak has signed the [Declaration on Open Science and Research 2020-2025](#).

Humak is already committed to the following national guidelines regarding Open Science:

- The Research Ethics Advisory Board's guideline on [Good scientific practice and procedures for handling misconduct and fraud in science](#).
- The Research Ethics Advisory Board's Guidelines on [The ethical principles of research with human participants and ethical review in the human sciences in Finland](#).

Humak has also started the work in developing its RDI impact assessment, data gathering processes and data exploitation, which has clear synergy with the CoARA Action Plan.

The aim of this CoARA Action Plan is to consolidate current Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) methods and implement additional steps for embedding CoARA commitments into Humak's daily operations. The cornerstone of the plan is to enhance the impact of research outcomes and ensure research quality. The execution of the Action Plan will begin in mid-2024.

3. Humak's Action Plan for Responsible Research Assessment 2024-2028

The starting point of the Action Plan is to document and evaluate Humak's current research and researcher evaluation processes. Based on this information possible development areas will be identified in accordance with the CoARA principles and the needed additions and developments are made to the RRA-processes. The renewed processes will be implemented into Humak's daily work via piloting process and evaluated accordingly.

Engagement, Dissemination and Promotion of Responsible Assessment

Action	Result/Milestone	Timetable	Responsibility
Commitment of resources to research assessment reform	Resource (human and other) commitment to the RRA work by the Humak Executive Team. Resources allocated for the whole duration of the Action Plan.	2024	Humak Executive Team

Establishing Humak's Responsible Research/er Assessment Working Group	Established Humak RRA Working Group for the whole duration of the Action Plan. WG consists of people from all relevant parts of Humak organisation.	2024	Humak Executive Team
Updating the Action Plan and progress reporting	Action Plan reviewed and updated (if needed) yearly by the Humak RRA Working Group. Progress regarding the RRA-work reported on a regular basis to the responsible director.	Yearly	Humak's Responsible Research/er Assessment Working Group
Communication and Cooperation	All relevant Humak-specific parties have been involved in the development work. Best practices and tools have been communicated internally and externally via relevant channels. Working in relevant networks and working groups (including the CoARA National Chapter Finland) throughout the RRA Action Plan process.	2024-2028	Humak's Responsible Research/er Assessment Working Group

Research assessment in Humak

Action	Result/Milestone	Timetable	Responsibility
Current status evaluation of RDI process in research assessment, key challenges and priorities identification	Written report of the current state, obstacles and possibilities of responsible research assessment in Humak including suggestions for further development in line with the CoARA principles.	2025	Humak's Responsible Research/er Assessment Working Group
RRA quality criteria and policy development and piloting in RDI	Humak's Responsible Research Assessment framework, policy and necessary tools developed, piloted and put into action. Guidance material provided in the Humak intranet and trainings organised for the relevant staff members. Model for RDI impact measurement, data collection and communication developed and deployed in the Humak RDI process and systems.	2025-2027	Humak's Responsible Research/er Assessment Working Group, Humak Development Services
Evaluation	Yearly evaluation of Humak Responsible Research Assessment	2028-	Humak's Responsible

	processes, criteria and tools. Possible suggestions for further development in line with the CoARA principles.		Research/er Assessment Working Group
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Researcher assessment in Humak

Action	Result/Milestone	Timetable	Responsibility
Current status evaluation of researcher assessment, key challenges and priorities identification	Written report of the current state, obstacles and possibilities of responsible researcher (and RDI-staff) assessment in Humak including suggestions for further development in line with the CoARA principles.	2025	Humak's Responsible Research/er Assessment Working Group
Development and piloting of UAS-specific researcher career path model in Humak	Researcher profile in Humak defined and career path model developed and piloted. Responsible Researcher Assessment policy, framework and necessary tools developed and deployed. Guidance material available for the recruiters/evaluators in the Humak intranet. Trainings organised for relevant staff members.	2025-2027	Humak's Responsible Research/er Assessment Working Group
Development and piloting of UAS-specific career path model for RDI Administrative staff	The need for UAS-specific career path model for RDI Administrative Staff identified, piloted and developed. Responsible Assessment framework and necessary tools developed and deployed. Guidance material available for the recruiters/evaluators in the Humak intranet. Trainings organised for relevant staff members.	2025-2027	Humak's Responsible Research/er Assessment Working Group
Evaluation	Yearly evaluation of Humak Responsible Researcher/RDI Administrative Staff Assessment processes, criteria and tools. Possible suggestions for further development in line with the CoARA principles.	2028-	Humak's Responsible Research/er Assessment Working Group

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The plan has been accepted by Humak Executive Team on 14th of May 2024 and will be updated when needed.